

Is it possible to propose a local hidden-variable framework that reproduces the predictions of quantum mechanics?

In Sakurai's book Modern Quantum Mechanics, section on Einstein's Locality Principle and Bell's Inequality (p.229), consider a trivial hidden-variable framework in which λ is uniformly distributed:

$$P[\hat{a}^+, \hat{b}^+] \leq P[\hat{a}^+, \hat{c}^+] + P[\hat{c}^+, \hat{b}^+]. \quad (1)$$

In this case, every possible outcome has an identical chance of occurring:

$$P[\hat{a}^+, \hat{b}^+] = P[\hat{a}^+, \hat{c}^+] = P[\hat{c}^+, \hat{b}^+] = \frac{2}{8}.$$

We then can write (1) as:

$$\frac{1}{2} \sin^2 \theta \leq \frac{1}{2} \sin^2 \theta + \frac{1}{2} \sin^2 \theta, \quad (2)$$

with $\theta = 45.0^\circ$.

Notice that (2) can be written as:

$$(\sin^2 \theta)^2 \leq \sin^2 \theta, \quad (3)$$

with $\theta = 45.0^\circ$.

The inequalities $(\sin^2 \theta)^2 \leq \sin^2 \theta$ and $\sin^2 \theta \leq |\sin \theta|$ are equivalent $\forall \theta \in \mathbb{R}^\circ$.

Consequently, from (3):

$$\sin^2 45.0^\circ \leq |\sin 45.0^\circ| \quad (4)$$

Then one can rewrite (4) as:

$$1 - \sin^2 45.0^\circ \leq \sin 45.0^\circ, \quad (5)$$

or even as:

$$1 - \sin 45.0^\circ \leq \sin^2 45.0^\circ. \quad (6)$$

And making use of the half-angle identity:

$$1 - \sin 45.0^\circ = 2 \sin^2 22.5^\circ, \quad (7)$$

we obtain from (6):

$$2 \sin^2 22.5^\circ \leq \sin^2 45.0^\circ. \quad (8)$$

Rearranging (8):

$$\frac{1}{2} \sin^2 22.5^\circ + \frac{1}{2} \sin^2 22.5^\circ \leq \frac{1}{2} \sin^2 45.0^\circ, \quad (9)$$

which are the quantum-mechanical predictions shown on p.230.